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DEVELOPMENT OF CONTROL SYSTEM FOR SMALL AUTONOMOUS UNDERWATER VEHICLE

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Abstract: This work proposes the development of a control system for an autonomous underwater vehicle dedicated to the observation of the oceans. The vehicle, a hybrid between Autonomous Underwater Vehicles and Autonomous Surface Vehicles, that moves on the surface of the sea and makes vertical immersions to obtain profiles of a water column, according to a pre-established plan. The displacement of the vehicle on the surface allows the navigation through GPS and telemetry communication by radio-modem. This control system has been divided into navigation, propulsion, safety and data acquisition subsystems.

Keywords: Vehicles, Autonomous, Control system, Oceans

I. Background and introduction

1. Ocean

An ocean, is a body of water that composes much of a planet's hydrosphere. On Earth, an ocean is one of the major conventional divisions of the World Ocean. These are, in

descending order by area, the Pacific, Atlantic, Indian, Southern (Antarctic), and Arctic Oceans. The word "ocean" is often used interchangeably with "sea" in American English. Strictly speaking, a sea is a body of water (generally a division of the world ocean) partly or fully enclosed by land, though "the sea" refers also to the oceans.

Saline water covers approximately 361,000,000 km² (139,000,000 sq mi) and is customarily divided into several principal oceans and smaller seas, with the ocean covering approximately 71% of Earth's surface and 90% of the Earth's biosphere. The ocean contains 97% of Earth's water, and oceanographers have stated that less than 5% of the World Ocean has been explored. The total volume is approximately 1.35 billion cubic kilometers (320 million cu mi) with an average depth of nearly 3,700 meters.

Fig 1: AUV function test in ocean for observation

2. Autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV)

An autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) is a robot that travels underwater without requiring input from an operator. AUVs constitute part of a larger group of undersea systems known as unmanned underwater vehicles, a classification that includes non-autonomous remotely operated underwater vehicles (ROVs) controlled and powered from the surface by an operator/pilot via an umbilical or using remote control. In military applications an AUV is more often referred to as an unmanned undersea vehicle (UUV). Underwater gliders are a subclass of AUVs

The first AUV was developed at the Applied Physics Laboratory at the University of Washington as early as 1957 by Stan Murphy, Bob Francois and later on, Terry Ewart. The "Special Purpose Underwater Research Vehicle", or SPURV, was used to study diffusion, acoustic transmission, and submarine wakes.

Other early AUVs were developed at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in the 1970s. One of these is on display in the Hart Nautical Gallery in MIT. At the same time, AUVs were also developed in the Soviet Union (although this was not commonly known until much later).

Scientists use AUVs to study lakes, the ocean, and the ocean floor. A variety of sensors can be affixed to AUVs to measure the concentration of various elements or compounds, the absorption or reflection of light, and the presence of microscopic life. Examples include conductivity-temperature-depth sensors (CTDs), fluorometers, and pH sensors. Additionally, AUVs can be configured as tow-vehicles to deliver customized sensor packages to specific locations.

Fig 2: SPURV being introduced in ocean environment for observation and testing

3. AUV Control system

A control system manages, commands, directs, or regulates the behavior of other devices or systems using control loops. It can range from a single home heating controller using a thermostat controlling a domestic boiler to large Industrial control systems which are used for controlling processes or machines.

For continuously modulated control, a feedback controller is used to automatically control a process or operation. The control system compares the value or status of the process variable (PV) being controlled with the desired value or set-point (SP), and applies the difference as a control signal to bring the process variable output of the plant to the same value as the set-point.

II. Research status and development trend at home and abroad

1. AUV research status and development trend at home and abroad

Here: Explorer (Tan Suo Zhe, 探索者) autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) is a Chinese AUV developed in the People's Republic of China (PRC), first entering service in November 1994.

Abroad: The first AUV was developed at the Applied Physics Laboratory at the University of Washington as early as 1957 by Stan Murphy, Bob Francois and later on, Terry Ewart. The "Special Purpose Underwater Research Vehicle", or SPURV, was used to study diffusion, acoustic transmission, and submarine wakes.

However, limited and limited technical conditions at that time, AUV is either too big or energy consumption problem is serious, until the 1980s, with the progress of new energy technology and microelectronics technology, AUV technical problems were solved. After the 1990s, the Research Boom of AUV was re-launched, and the United States, Britain, Germany, Japan, Canada, Italy and other countries have stepped up research and development efforts on AUV. From the initial experimental AUV, to the production and application of engineered products, most countries AUV manufacturing has entered the modular, serialized and commercial stage, the most representative of which are the REMUS series AUV and Bluefin series AUV.

Fig 3: REMUS 100

AUV's control system research status and development trend

Several searches have been carried out on the AUV control system for hardware and software.

a) Hardware

About hardware we can say that, Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) can manage their operation by reliable programming of high-level controllers that make the device able to maneuver even under unpredicted conditions. However, decision-making issues should be adequately addressed for consistent operation, among them safe navigation through potential obstacles. During the last few years, number of approaches have been proposed to tackle this problem but they mainly suffer from relatively slow response when there is a real need for quick decision-making. In the designed prototype, two cameras have been implemented, one on the top and the one on the bottom, to collect data from the Environment in order to detect obstacles. Furthermore, knowing that sensing in aquatic environments may result in image distortion occurring by refraction of light, a robust image processing technique was developed to process data through Proportional-Integral- Derivative (PID) controllers. A technique combining color and Local Binary Pattern (LBP) characteristics was developed to efficiently describe the target and a tracking algorithm built by using these features. Tests under real conditions demonstrated the proposed approach.

b) Software

About the software control of AUV we can say that, Early AUVs were totally reliant on their onboard software for decision making, and until recently, undersea wireless communications were effectively impossible. Once an early AUV was launched, there was no opportunity to change its programming or otherwise alter its mission. At best, operators had a tracking system so they could observe where the AUV went. Today, with the evolution of the technology and the hard work of researchers many things are possible with AUVs and they become more autonomous with the possibility to accomplish more than one task at the same time.

c) Control method

The research project named Development of a Control System for an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle was made by I.Masmitja, G. Masmitja, J. González, S. Shariat-Panahi,

S. Gomariz, SARTI Research Group of the Department of Electronic Engineering of the Technical University of Catalonia; Avda; Victor Balaguer s/n 08800 Vilanova i la Barcelona in Spain. This work proposed the development of a control system for an autonomous underwater vehicle dedicated to the observation of the oceans. The vehicle, a hybrid between Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) and Autonomous Surface Vehicles (ASV), moves on the surface of the sea and makes vertical immersions to obtain profiles of a water column, according to a pre-established plan. The displacement of the vehicle on the surface allowed the navigation through GPS and telemetry communication by radio-modem. That control system has been divided into navigation, propulsion, safety and data acquisition subsystems.

The research contents and research method

Overall design of the AUV and structure design.

Work Innovation Point

The robot has a very high underwater applicability, AUV overall modular design, can be convenient to disassemble and add modules with other functions, reduce hardware costs and maintenance difficulty, while improving hardware versatility to meet different underwater exploration needs.

The robot attitude control flexible, long body shape, torpedo type, equipped with 3 propellers and 4 rudder control movement, can enter the narrow corner for exploration, can complete the steering and power positioning, with good task adaptability.

Cannot get GPS positioning under water, the use of the robot with navigation instruments for space calculation and calibration through the surface.

AUV has a variety of operating modes: surface wireless remote-control operation mode, fiber remote control operation mode and underwater autonomous operation mode. Adapt to the needs of the job without conditions. According to the job requirements, can provide open hardware interface and open source interface software code cluster application: small size, flexible

operation, equipped with audio communication machine can achieve "bee swarm" job.

How the design works

The probe robot AUV consists of two parts: the surface control system and the underwater motion system.

The surface control system is responsible for the transmission of control information, real-time monitoring and display ingress motion attitude, lowering machine safety alarm information and underwater video image information, and can be operated by computer software button stos and keyboard, and the corresponding action is transmitted to the lower computer by communication in the form of instructions.

The underwater control system is responsible for collecting the information of the safety alarm module in the electronic cabin and sending it to the upper machine, and receiving the upper-position control instructions to complete the corresponding action, and the lower-position machine integrates with the electronic equipment in the body-resistant electronic svemon compartment, with the micro-controller as the core, the peripheral is The DCDC power module, the depth meter, the leak collection module, the temperature and humidity detection module, Communication modules, etc.

AUV function

This work propose the development of a control system for a small autonomous underwater vehicle dedicated to the observation of the oceans.

The work of this subject discuss a development of control system for small autonomous underwater vehicle.

The design sought to develop a simple, easy-to-use and inexpensive AUV with a level of functionality that have enough modularity in order to adapt to different missions

Object	Index
Structural form	torpedo type
Design size (cm)	120 x 13 x 13
Working water depth (m)	20

Speed (kn)	1.5
Net weight in the air (kg)	6.7kg
Power	12V
Propulsion	Down 2, Main Push, Rudd leaf x 4
Camera	HD Camera 1
Control Mode	Manual/Automatic Control

Fig4: Key Technical Parameters of Probed AUV

This AUV consists of two parts: the surface control system and the underwater motion system.

The following function are implemented:

The control software use wireless communication to issue instructions to control the movement and operation of the AUV body underwater;

Through the coordination of the propeller and the rudder leaf, the AUV body is flexible in the freedom of lifting, retreating, swinging, etc.

The control system is divided into two modes of manual control and automatic control, manual control can be operated by reference to the attitude data and images transmitted to the control interface in real time, and automatic control can be used to trigger the key to achieve fixed deep navigation, directional navigation;

High-definition camera can make a full range of detailed observation of underwater objects, can take real-time photos of objects that need to be watched, and transmit and record underwater observation video in real time.

Carry GPS, guide and other underwater navigation equipment for underwater navigation.

Fig 5: AUV side view

Fig 6: AUV Top view

Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUV) are designed for the investigation of underwater environments without a permanent control from a human operator. Working with AUVs requires a preliminary mission planning and loading of the planned survey. This inertial navigation system is also to send information to the lower machine control system, and then through the lower position receive the information for simple verification, through communication with the upper computer is verified data sent to the upper machine, and then the upper computer protocol parsing and processing, and the information displayed to the upper computer interface.

AUVs can be launched and recovered from shore, jetties, small vessels, providing versatility in use on a wide range of applications.

the main thrust here is to design an AUV that can be used for underwater exploration sets to assist our marine researchers and operators; especially since we want to replace the man who has the base did this job of exploration by risking his daily life with limits by a machine whose abilities and efficiency are by far better.

2. Control system

Underwater robot control system is the core of the whole system. The control system mainly includes the surface control system and the underwater control system, the surface control system is composed of computer, the upper computer and other equipment, the underwater control system is composed of underwater camera, underwater lamp, thruster, various kinds of sensors and so on. The surface control system adopts the upper-seat monitoring software

developed by Qt, uses the underwater control system as the core of the digital transmission radio, and can use optical fiber communication to realize the function of large data transmission

Fig7: AUV control system

a) Hardware design of the control system of AUV

The underwater control system is controlled by the micro-controller control module, which uses the stm32f429IGT6 chip as the control chip, the stm32f429IGT6 has high performance; It can analyze communication system, control system, attitude adjustment subsystem, underwater equipment control subsystem and underwater data acquisition processing module according to the characteristics of hybrid drive and motion mode of underwater unmanned vehicle, optimize the multi-modal control algorithm of underwater unmanned vehicle, and ensure that the control algorithm has good extensibility and fault tolerance, so as to make the multi-modal motion control of UV more convenient.

The control system is equipped with multiple 232 communication module and 485 communication modules, and the rich communication outside is set to control system communication provides great convenience. At the same time, also provides complete communication conditions for the navigation module.

AUV body is equipped with various kinds of sensors, including GPS positioning system, habitual navigation system, leakage into water and many other safety sensors.

Fig9: Dashboard software program flowchart

b₁) The upper computer

In the upper machine control platform, the AUV surface control system is mainly responsible for the release of navigational mission and the monitoring of the operating status of underwater robots. In the remote-control operation mode, the robot status information is transmitted back to the surface control unit in real time, in the status information, the surface control system software use Windows as the operating system, and based on the MOOS (Mission Orientated Operating Suite) platform is written in the C-language in the QT development environment, and the human-computer interface design is carried out.

The AUV body motion attitude, the lowering machine safety alarm information and the underwater video image information are displayed through real-time monitoring of the upper computer, and the button and key action on the console panel are collected, and the corresponding action transmitted to the lower computer by numerical communication in the form of instructions.

Fig 10: Inertial navigation data display

- 1- Menu
- 2- Parameters
- 3- Send and receive message with the AUV
- 4- Push button
- 5- Temperature
- 6- Depth
- 7- Three angles (Course, pitch and roll)

- 8- Humidity
- 9- Alarms
- 10- Characteristics
- 11- Direction observer

b2) The lower computer

Dynamic positioning (DP) is a computer-controlled system to automatically maintain a vessel's position and heading by using its own propellers and thruster. Position reference sensors, combined with wind sensors, motion sensors and gyro-compasses, provide information to the computer pertaining to the vessel's position and the magnitude and direction of environmental forces affecting its position.

A proportional–integral–derivative controller continuously calculates an error value $e(t)$ as the difference between a desired set-point (SP) and a measured process variable (PV) and applies a correction based on proportional, integral, and derivative terms (denoted P, I, and D respectively), hence the name. In practical terms it automatically applies accurate and responsive correction to a control function. An everyday example is the cruise control on an AUV, where ascending a hill would lower speed if only constant engine power were applied. The controller's PID algorithm restores the measured speed to the desired speed with minimal delay and overshoot by increasing the power output of the engine.

Fig 11: Definite depth double closed loop PID control algorithm

The two closed-loop PID control algorithm of speed closed ring and around closed loop is used. The control board directly receives the feedback of the thruster and the flight information, the real-time is better, the speed closed-loop PID control algorithm and the navigation PID control algorithm are realized in the control board, and the navigation double-closed-loop PID control algorithm is framed as follows figure 11.

Fig 12: Fixed-navigation double-closed-loop PID control algorithm

The double closed-loop PID control algorithm of speed closed ring and deep closed loop is used. Also, in the control board to achieve the speed closed-loop PID control algorithm and depth of PID control algorithm, fixed-depth double closed-loop PID control algorithm frame diagram as shown in Figure 12.

4. Experiments

1. Thruster performance test
2. Rudder test
3. GPS function test
4. The inertia module function test
5. Depth gauge test
5. System assembly
6. Pool commissioning

III. Possible problem or difficulties and their arrangement

A major limiting factor to current AUVs is propulsion and energy efficiency. With the energy density of currently available power storage systems, AUVs are limited in their operating time.

- ❖ The main problem is to study both, hardware and software.
- ❖ The AUV required many knowledges.
- ❖ The propulsion and energy efficiency.
- ❖ Ocean with high water-column turbidity.
- ❖ Read many articles and learn from many tutorials.

- ❖ The implementation of PID controller will help us to manage accurately the device.

- ❖ The screw propeller is one of the best solutions to move a small AUV easily.

Reducing an AUV's size and cost limits the amount of energy it can store in the form of batteries, which restricts it to slower cruising speeds over shorter ranges. Slow cruising speeds and short ranges inevitably diminish the usefulness of small AUVs in the ocean environment where typical currents are 10 cm/s or greater, and length scales are of the order of one to thousands of kilometers. However, small lakes provide an environment in which a slow AUV with limited range and speed can have many applications. Length scales of phenomena in lakes are of the same order as the basin scale or less, limiting the required AUV range. Risk of loss is reduced since small lakes present a limited search region (in depth and horizontal extent) should the vehicle disappear. A Pinger locator system is still required to locate a disabled vehicle in any sizable lake.

However, achieving greater vehicle speed and range requires more stored energy. On-board energy storage capacity can be increased with either larger or higher energy density batteries. Both options lead to increased cost of operation.

IV. Result of the research

This work provide a control system for a small autonomous underwater vehicle. The developed platform is robust, relatively small and lightweight, factors which facilitate its manageability and operability. It incorporates an embedded computer that manages the navigation, propulsion and safety systems of the vehicle. Given their high performance, the incorporation of trajectory control algorithms is feasible. Also, specific hardware and software will be design for the correct operation of the sensors and thrusters.

Surface systems include computers and water control software. The AUV body motion attitude, the lowering machine safety alarm information and the underwater video image information display through real-time monitoring of the upper computer, and the button and key action on the console panel are collected, and the corresponding action transmitted to the lower computer by numerical communication in the form of instruction.

Underwater robot control system is the core of the whole system. The control system mainly includes the surface control system and the underwater control system.

With improvements in acoustic systems, it is now possible to transmit small amounts of data between AUVs and their operators. Vehicle status, such as depth, battery level, and even some sensor data, can be sent from the AUV to the mission control computer onshore or on a boat. Low-level decisions, such as "speed up" or "turn," are made by the computer and software on the AUV, but operators can transmit higher-level decisions, like "stop" and "come home." Operators can also change the survey area while an AUV is submerged. Even though AUVs may receive messages from an operator, the operator is not driving.

Conclusion

The purpose of this paper is to develop a control system for small autonomous underwater vehicle for underwater exploration, on the basis of full research on the current situation of autonomous underwater vehicle research at home and abroad, a set of design scheme for control system of small autonomous underwater vehicle sits is put forward, and the design and production of the hardware part and software part of surface control system and underwater control system is completed. Including the design and production of autonomous underwater vehicle is independently completed.

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Dedication

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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